

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PARTICIPATION OF AGGREGATORS IN ELECTRICITY MARKETS OF LOCAL ELECTRICITY SYSTEM

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Abstract

The local electricity system is a decentralized network. To achieve effective interaction between suppliers and consumers in the operation of local systems in electricity markets, a load aggregator is needed. The goal of the aggregator is to maximize its profit in the day-ahead energy market. The article examines the features of the participation of load aggregators in day-ahead electricity markets and presents an analysis of the aggregator's operation with forecasted load schedules when applying different demand response programs. The daily load schedule and 4 load change strategies (Load Curtailment, Load Shifting, Flexible Load Shape, Energy Arbitrage, Utilizing Onsite Generation, Utilizing ES System) for a local electricity system consisting of a centralized grid, an energy storage system, and a solar generator are considered. An analysis of the impact of different load change strategies on the total daily cost of electricity showed that all strategies will lead to a decrease in cost. The best results were shown by Load Curtailment strategies and Energy Arbitrage.

Keywords: local electricity system, aggregator, electricity market, demand response.

The integration of distributed energy resources and new technological resources into the existing energy system and energy markets poses a number of challenges, as operators usually do not have adequate monitoring or control mechanisms for low-voltage networks.

Demand response (DR) is a mechanism that allows electricity consumers to adjust their consumption in response to changes in electricity prices or to signals from the electricity grid operator. The purpose of this adjustment is to ensure a balance between supply and demand in the electricity grid, which can help reduce the need for expensive and polluting peaking power plants and improve the reliability and efficiency of the electricity system [1].

An aggregator is an important link in dispatching, as it manages the capacity of distributed facilities, consumption, generation, and storage of energy. For market participants, this provides an opportunity to generate additional revenues, and for the transmission system operator, more balancing capacity and a simplified dispatching structure.

Aggregators that are designed to work with specific distributed energy technologies usually do not participate in the same markets. Aggregators that operate and are defined in the context of renewable energy, such as wind turbine or small solar power plant owners, sell electricity in long-term bilateral contract markets or short-term markets. RES are inflexible sources of electricity, as they depend on the stochasticity of wind and sun, so they cannot be used as providers of flexibility

in balancing markets. Distributed storage or electric vehicles require the operation of an aggregator operating in short-term markets or offering its flexibility in balancing markets [1-14].

The following general models of aggregation implementation can be distinguished [2, 3]:

1. Supplier/aggregator: one business entity provides work in different markets, suppliers simultaneously provide electricity supply and aggregation services to ensure additional flexibility.

2. Independent aggregator: the consumer uses the services of two market entities, where the supplier provides electricity supply, the aggregator separately provides system flexibility.

Two groups of such models can also be distinguished [4]:

- Without balance responsibility: the aggregator is not responsible for the balance and is not obliged to send day-ahead plans to the system operator.

- With balance responsibility: the aggregator must be the responsible party, and it is obliged to send day-ahead plans to the system operator. In this case, services can be provided without imbalance correction. The aggregator does not compensate the supplier for the imbalance caused. Thus, it is exempted from payments for imbalance. Aggregation model with imbalance correction. In this case, the aggregator is responsible for the imbalance caused by the supplier and compensates for it.

The advantages of the supplier/aggregator models are easy integration into the current market model and balancing scheme with minimal regulatory changes.

On the other hand, markets with a small number of retail companies will not experience significant changes when it comes to increasing liquidity and competitiveness. The main part of the revenues for such companies will still come from energy supply.

The advantages of the independent aggregator model for small markets are increased market competition and the development of new business models in terms of technologies and services. Specialized companies for aggregation and flexibility of distributed energy resources will also appear, which can lead to more efficient operation of the system and the market. The main disadvantage is the need for a comprehensive change in legislation and the market model.

The main advantage of an independent aggregator, which is not responsible for imbalances, is the simplic-

ity and low costs of entering the market as a new participant, but, on the other hand, it complicates the balancing scheme, which can lead to economic losses for some market participants.

An independent aggregator with responsibility for imbalance but without its correction can also be quite simple to implement. However, if the aggregator has to pay the system operator for the imbalance it causes, it will have no economic motivation to enter the market, which makes this model unstable.

An independent aggregator with balance responsibility and imbalance correction, on the contrary, has an economic motivation to enter the market, but the main disadvantage of such an aggregator model is the calculation of compensation costs between the aggregator and the supplier. The question also arises as to how imbalances will be settled if the aggregator and the supplier are in two different balancing groups.

A schematic distribution of aggregation models is shown in Figure 1 [4].

Figure 1. Possible models for implementing aggregation

The wide range of DRG technologies leads to a wide range of definitions of aggregators (Fig. 1). When aggregators are defined in the context of renewable energy generation (RES), such as small photovoltaics or wind turbines, they sell their electricity on long-term markets or on short-term ones. Since renewables are inherently inflexible (dependent on wind and sun), they are not used as flexibility providers in balancing markets or as flexibility sinks in intraday markets. Distributed energy storage, stationary DR or electric vehicles (EVs) require an aggregator that can efficiently buy/sell

energy on short-term markets or offer its flexibility on balancing markets as an ancillary service. Traditional suppliers buy electricity from their inflexible customers on long-term markets. If consumers C integrate demand response, generation or storage into their technologies, they become active consumers (AC). Such consumers have the ability to feed power into the grid and respond to grid/market signals, so they also need an aggregator that can offer such flexibility for energy exchange [4].

Figure 2. Aggregators in electricity markets

Demand-side management of electricity is usually a shift of consumption from peak to off-peak hours. In turn, energy efficiency is a gradual reduction in electricity consumption, which is achieved by introducing more efficient and economical equipment and gradually abandoning less efficient equipment without reducing functionality. Energy efficiency measures depending on the hours of use of energy-efficient equipment can reduce peak consumption. In turn, demand management can affect total electricity consumption. Although in general demand management does not have a significant impact on total consumption in terms of the day, some demand management programs can even increase consumption during off-peak hours and in some cases increase total electricity consumption. In this case, the increase in consumption must be justified from an economic point of view by reducing the cost of off-peak electricity or reducing fuel costs. In European markets, joint optimization of demand-side management and energy efficiency programs for maximum combined effect is widespread [5, 6]. Suppliers have the ability to act as load aggregators, organize their own demand management programs, and encourage independent aggregators to participate in their own programs.

The purpose of the article is to consider the features of the participation of load aggregators in day-ahead electricity markets and analyze the operation of the aggregator with forecasted load schedules when applying various demand response programs.

The essence of dynamic pricing is to offer monetary benefits to consumers (using the aggregator) for redistributing their load consumption and balancing demand in the electricity network. DR with the aggregator enabled should guarantee a reduction in the total cost of consumption by shifting the load of consumers taking into account the preferences of consumers.

For example, consumers report their load characteristics to the aggregator the day before consumption, and prices are calculated one day-ahead.

Aggregators need to forecast mandatory prices to determine energy consumption for the current time interval and future time intervals. The overall goal is to develop stable and coordinated strategies for dynamic pricing and demand response in electricity networks.

The interaction between the aggregator and the consumer can be divided into the following types:

- Direct load control – the traditional demand management method, according to which the load is controlled by the aggregator at all times, but the consumer is not rewarded at all.

- Price-based control. Currently, many aggregators provide their consumers with manual or automatic price-based programs. With this strategy, the consumer can be rewarded in many different ways, for example, the consumer will receive a fixed price for reducing the load. On the other hand, most aggregators offer a dynamic pricing mechanism, and therefore the consumer will be rewarded with a price based on the real-time electricity market.

- An incentive-based pricing mechanism allows consumers to directly interact with the energy market by betting against having their electricity disconnected.

Similarly, contracts between consumers and the aggregator can be bilateral or unilateral. If it is a bilateral contract, then it is an agreement in which the aggregator promises to pay an incentive to the consumer, and in return, the consumer promises to disconnect or regulate the shared loads to reduce the required consumption. However, if it is a unilateral contract, then only the aggregator promises to pay the incentive to the consumer if he disconnects or regulates his load. This means that the consumer does not control the load, and the aggregator must pay the incentive to the consumer if he disconnects the load.

Consider a generalized model of a local electricity system load aggregator with all possible demand response options for day-ahead market participation. Six load shifting strategies [7-16]:

- 1) Load Curtailment (LC). The LC strategy reduces the total electricity consumption in the scheduled DR program without shifting the load to any other time period.

- 2) Load Shifting (LS). In the LS strategy, customers change their electricity consumption schedule to other hours. For example, a customer may postpone the operation of their appliances to later hours of the day, or an industrial enterprise may shift the batch production process to other hours of the day or other days of the week.

- 3) Flexible Load Shape (FLS) is an advanced level that controls the overall shape of load demand through system scheduling.

- 4) Energy Arbitrage (EA) is a DSM strategy that is achieved by saving energy during periods of lower energy costs versus periods of higher energy costs. Energy arbitrage is mainly achieved through energy storage devices such as batteries, supercapacitors and electric vehicles.

- 5) Utilizing Onsite Generation (OG): In the OG strategy, customers reduce their load by switching on a local or backup generator to supply some or all of their own electricity loads. Although participants may experience a minor interruption in their electricity consumption, their net load will be reduced in the DR program. Therefore, using off-site generation is equivalent to reducing the customer's load from the perspective of the power system, although on-site generation may have its own technical limitations for the customer to participate in DR.

- 6) Utilizing ES System (ES). In the ES system strategy, customers use their ES system to supply some or all of their electricity needs during the DR program. The ES can be a large modular storage device or an aggregated capacity of small distributed storage systems. By using ES, the net load of DR participants will be reduced as ES is discharged and will increase as ES is accrued in energy markets.

The considered load-shifting strategies help aggregators to coordinate local electricity systems in a more comprehensive way. Aggregators use the monitoring, measurement and verification processes that are necessary for the implementation of response programs in electricity markets.

The goal of the aggregator is to maximize its profit (total revenue minus costs) in the day-ahead energy

market. The aggregator makes a profit by offering (selling) a demand response strategy in the energy market and paying the response program participants for hourly/daily load changes. The incentive for aggregation is the difference between the prices of the response

$$\sum_{t \in N_T} \left[\rho_t (LR_t^{LC} + LR_t^{LS} + LR_t^{FLS} + LR_t^{EA} + LR_t^{OG} + LR_t^{EC}) - (CLR_t^{LC} + CLR_t^{LS} + CLR_t^{FLS} + CLR_t^{EA} + CLR_t^{OG} + CLR_t^{EC}) \right] \rightarrow \max,$$

where N_T – the time range of the next day, equal to 24, ρ_t – the market price, LR – the load change according to the CLR strategy, CLR – the cost of this change.

The first part in the objective function is the revenue from the sale of the combined volumes of the six load reduction strategies, and the second part are the costs of paying contract customers for load reduction.

Consider the daily load schedule and 4 load change strategies (Fig. 3-4) for a local electricity system consisting of a grid, an energy storage system, and a solar generator. Strategy 5 has a similar schedule to

programs in contracts with consumers and the hourly market prices of electricity.

The objective function for the aggregator’s self-scheduling is maximized as follows, taking into account the 6 strategies considered above:

strategy 1, the consumer decides whether to cover the load reduction with his own needs. Strategy 6 is similar in strategy to 4 for the system under consideration, the consumer’s battery can be charged from the local network at low prices during the day, and discharged for his own needs at night. Therefore, it was chosen as an example of the application of the first four considered strategies.

Figure 3 b shows a graph of the predicted value of the cost of electricity per hour for the daily schedule (Fig. 3 a) and offered by the aggregator, taking into account the limitations of the application of strategy 1 (LC) and the consumer’s ability to change the load.

Figure 3 Research results: daily power schedule (a), cost schedule (b)

Similarly, Figure 2 shows the application of strategies 2-4 (LS, FLS, EA).

The aggregator offers consumers 4 load-shifting options, based on four different load-shedding strategies, and seeks to maximize its day-ahead profit

through price-based planning for forecasted load schedules.

Figure 4 Research results

Table 1 shows the indicators obtained when modeling the operation of the aggregator. When calculating the cost, values were taken from sources [17].

The best results are achieved when reducing the load. But in reality this is achieved by the fact that the

consumer consumed less. With the same consumer power, energy arbitrage is the best for the considered case.

Table1.

Research results				
	Average power, kW	Maximum power, kW	Minimum power, kW	Total cost per day \$
Without DR	100	190	30	478
LS	95	190	20	443
LC	100	190	30	444
FLS	100	180	30	450
EA	100	190	30	434

Conclusions.

Aggregation of distributed energy resources is a necessity for an energy-efficient and ecological energy

system. Using the DR program provides benefits to both consumers and the grid.

The features of the participation of load aggregators in day-ahead electricity markets are considered.

The aggregator controls the load of consumers, developing a control and monitoring strategy to maximize its own income, minimize the supplier's costs and provide incentives for consumers.

The work of the aggregator with forecasted load schedules when applying various demand response programs is analyzed.

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